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DIGITAL SHADOWS: THE PERCEPTIONS AND PREVALENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA SHAMING AMONG EDUCATORS

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Abstract

Anchored on Goffman's Theory of Stigma, this study investigates social media shaming among teachers at a community college in Leyte by examining its incidence, emotional impact, professional effects, and reputation damage. It focuses on how educators perceive social media shaming, the groups most targeted, and the relationship between perceptions and experiences. A quantitative descriptive design was used, with data collected from 30 faculty members through a structured questionnaire and analyzed using SPSS with descriptive statistics, correlation, and ANOVA.

Key findings show that social media shaming impacts teachers' mental health, job security, and public reputation with female teachers reporting more emotional intensity than male teachers. While educators of all backgrounds see shaming examples around them, the occurrence of shaming events did not vary depending on age, sex, department, or degree. Although there is weak positive correlation between perceived prevalence and actual occurring events suggests perceptions are likely out of touch from their experiences. In conclusion, the study shows social media shaming events are damaging from an emotional and professional standpoint, however, the perceptions gathered about their occurrences were broader than the actual experience. Recommendations are for institutions to introduce strategies to protect educators by way of digital literacy training, mental health services, and the developing of policy/training.

Keywords: social media shaming, perceptions, prevalence, reputation damage, professional effects

INTRODUCTION

The increasing number of social media users has dug a momentous value in modern education that influences the student educators' communication, collaboration, and access to information. It changes how we communicate, connect, and consume information in the modern digital age. According to Chaffey (2025), 5.24 billion people of a global population, which is equivalent to 63.9%, are the active users of social media that spends approximately 2 hours a day. This increasing dominance highlights the role of social media in everyday life including education. Social media influences educational institutions to improve their efforts and community interaction, using platforms such as Facebook to target the communication and participation among the students, parents, and the educators.

The integration of social media in education offers a relevant benefit such as improving the live communication, it enables the online learning communities, also in giving access to various and timely learning resources beyond the traditional textbooks.

According to the Revankar and Madrekar (2025), students who says that social media helps them to learn better is 45%, and teachers who say that it helps them improve their communication between educators and students is 74%. Social media is said to support collaborative learning, learning critical thinking, and student engagement, especially in secondary and tertiary settings.

However, the effect of social media on academic achievement and students' well-being is quite complicated. Based on the research of Gordon and Ohannessian (2023), the increase in social media use of an early adolescent decreases the academic performance, it underscores the potential challenges that are associated with the frequent use of the platform.

In the Philippines, public shaming of teachers is an immersing issue. According to the report of Manila Bulletin, such incidents caused teachers to undergo severe stress, fear, and helpless feelings. It could be a distressing experience for teachers who experienced it may face a bigger impact such as discipline, professional reputation, and put their job at risk. Due to these attacks online, a lot of people are urging teachers who are involved to resign and revoke their licenses. The study of Lubid (2024) points that shaming practices are already embedded in Philippine educational culture.

The study of Makiling (2024) research shows how Filipino high school teachers are being disparaged online. At other locations, this intensifies into professional and personal assaults that disrupt their lives and brains all over the field. This study focuses on the psychological toll that online humiliation takes on educators. Undoubtedly, the purpose of this study was to learn more about the general opinions of teachers through interviews. Teachers are now frequently the target of personal and professional jokes on social media. For professionals like teachers, they bear what is essentially an intolerable mental burden.

There is little information available about the prevalence and extent of any effects that an educator experiences, so this study investigates ways to support their school in finding better supports and policies. Further, the results may inform school administrators and policy makers to establish explicit rules and simplify reporting procedures and professional development programs that will not only protect teachers from abusive online care, but also help create a culture of respect and responsibility in online environments.

Statement of the Problem

This study investigates the impact of online shaming in social media among teachers, as well as their consciousness of its effect on their emotional life and professional behaviors, which includes his/her own self-image

Specifically, this paper sought to address the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1 age
 - 1.2 sex
 - 1.3 educational attainment
 - 1.4 college department

2. What is the impact of social media shaming of teachers' perception in terms of:
 - 2.1 emotional and psychological impact
 - 2.2 Professional Reputation and Career Stability
 - 2.3 Public Attitudes Toward Teachers
 - 2.4 Response and Support Systems?

3. What is the prevalence of social media shaming against teachers in terms of:

- 3.1 Viral Post and Hashtags
- 3.2 Public Callouts,
- 3.3 emotions and reputation
- 3.4 Increase in Digital Footprint Monitoring?

4. Is there a significant difference between teachers' perceptions of social media shaming and their demographic profile?

5. Is there a significant difference between the prevalence of social media shaming on teachers and their demographic profile?

6. Is there a significant difference between perception and prevalence among educators?

7. Based on the results, what interventions can be proposed to prevent social media shaming in the academe?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used descriptive quantitative research to examine the issue of social media shaming faced by instructors at a community college. It explored how frequently teachers experienced social media shaming and its effects on their perspectives and emotions related to their profession. Data were collected through a survey questionnaire administered to full-time faculty members. Convenience sampling was employed, including only staff who were available and willing to participate.

Locale of the Study

This research took place at a local college in Leyte. This institution functions as a close-knit academic community which creates a suitable environment to study teachers' perceptions towards social media shaming. The combination of virtual and physical relationships within these environments potentially influences how educators handle public criticism.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents were 30 instructors currently teaching at a certain local college in Leyte. They were selected through a convenience sampling. The sample was intended to be diverse by department, teaching experience, and level of exposure to digital interactions.

Research Instruments

This study used a structured questionnaire for the collection of quantitative data from college teaching staff. The instrument consisted of three sections. The first which asked for information on age, sex, educational attainment, and department. The second examined how often they experienced social media shaming through a Likert type scale. Lastly, the third looked at teachers' emotional and professional responses to social media shaming also through a Likert scale.

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Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher formally requested permission from the College administration to obtain the necessary data. Upon approval, the researchers informed the department heads so they can inform faculty of the study. Faculty from different departments were invited to participate in the research on a voluntary basis, with confidentiality assured. After signing informed consent forms, participants received a standardized survey, in paper form. The survey found out teachers' opinion of social media shaming, and the occurrences and effects of that activity. Participants were given 1-2 weeks to complete the survey with reminders sent appropriately. All data collected were saved securely and used exclusively for academic research.

Method of Scoring and Interpretation

Likert-scale were used to score the data gathered from the survey questionnaire. The value of a number corresponding to its place on the scale.

Following scoring, the researchers determined each item's mean score and total size to calculate teachers' perceptions and the perceived frequency of shaming on social media. A high perceived frequency was indicated by the high mean scores. whereas low mean scores indicated a perception that was less common.

- 4.25 – 5.00: Strongly Agree / Always
- 3.50 – 4.24: Agree / Often
- 2.50- 3.49: Disagree / Rarely
- 1.00 – 2.49: Strongly Disagree /Never

Ethical Consideration

All respondents were provided with an informed consent which included the purpose of the study, what rights they as respondents had, and details of what we did to protect their privacy. Also participation was completely voluntary and they were made aware that they may at any time choose to withdraw and data were securely stored.

Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics was used to summarize demographic information and responses of participants. teaching profession. The relationship between the experience of shaming, and the emotional or professional consequences of that experience was analyzed using Pearson correlation statistics, with results at a 0.05 significance level. Careful data analysis, carried out in SPSS, is useful in reducing error and improving reliability.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents

AGE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
20-29	14	46.7 %
30-39	12	40.0 %
40-49	4	13.3 %

50 yrs. above	0	0
TOTAL	30	100%
SEX		
MALE	13	43.3
FEMALE	17	56.7
TOTAL	30	100%
ACADEMIC DEPARTMENT		
CASE	10	33.3
COHME	7	23.3
CITE	6	20
CCJE	7	23.3
TOTAL	30	100%
EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT		
DOCTORATE DEGREE	2	6.7
MA w/ DOCTORAL UNITS	3	10
MASTER'S DEGREE	6	20
BS w/ MA UNITS	12	40
BACHELOR'S DEGREE	7	23.3
TOTAL	30	100%

As depicted in Table 1. most of the teachers were ranging from 20-29 years old (46.7%) and 30-39 years of age (40%), only few were age 40-49 years old (13.3%) and none of the teaching staff were age 50 years and above. It is clearly shown in the Table that there are more female teachers (56.7%) who partake compared to males which is (43.3%).

Moreover, data on their college department, show that the huge group came from the College of Arts, Sciences, and Education or CASE at 33.3%, followed by College of Hospitality Management and Entrepreneurship or COHME at 23.3% College of Criminal Justice Education (23.3%), and College of Information Technology Education at 20%).

Finally, it is also revealed that most of the respondents holds a BS with MA units (40%), followed by the bachelor's degree holders (23.3%) and Master's degree holders which is 20%, while there were only few who had the MA with Doctoral Units which is 10% and Doctorate Degree holders of 6.7%.

TABLE 2.1. EMOTIONAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL IMPACT

Emotional and Psychological Impact	Mean	Adjectival Description
1. I believe social media shaming negatively affects teachers' mental health.	3.67	Strongly agree
2. Teachers experience increased stress due to online criticism.	3.63	Strongly agree
3. Public shaming on social media lowers teachers' self-confidence.	3.47	Strongly agree
4. Social media shaming makes teachers feel isolated from their peers.	3.17	Agree
5. Online shaming affects teachers' motivation to perform their duties.	2.93	Agree
AVERAGE	3.37	Strongly agree

TABLE 2.2. RESPONSE AND SUPPORT SYSTEM

Response and Support Systems	Mean	Adjectival Description
1. Schools should provide more support to teachers who experienced social media shaming.	3.83	Strongly agree
2. Legal protections should be strengthened to safeguard teachers from social media attacks.	3.86	Strongly agree
3. There should be clear school policies addressing social media shaming of teachers.	3.83	Strongly agree
4. Support from colleagues helps teachers cope with online criticism.	3.7	Agree

5. Mental health services should be offered to teachers who have been shamed on social media.	3.7	Agree
AVERAGE	3.79	Strongly agree

TABLE 2.3. PROFESSIONAL AND CAREER STABILITY

Professional Reputation and Career Stability	Mean	Adjectival Description
1. Social media shaming damages a teacher's reputation in the community.	3.63	Strongly agree
2. Public criticism on social media can lead to disciplinary actions against teachers.	3.2	Agree
3. Parents and students change their perception of a teacher based on online criticism.	3.2	Agree
4. Social media posts about teachers can influence school administration decisions.	3.06	Agree
5. A teacher's career opportunities may be affected by social media shaming.	3.36	Strongly agree
AVERAGE	3.59	Strongly agree

TABLE 2.4. PUBLIC ATTITUDES TOWARD EDUCATORS

Public Attitudes Toward Educators	MEAN	Adjectival Description
1. Social media influences how the public views teachers as professionals.	3.5	AGREE
2. Viral posts criticizing teachers contribute to a decline in respect for the profession.	3.4	AGREE

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3. Negative online comments shape how students interact with teachers.	3.03	AGREE
4. Publicized mistakes on social media make it harder for teachers to regain trust.	3.16	AGREE
5. Society should be more understanding of teachers who are criticized online.	3.26	STRONGLY AGREE
AVERAGE	3.27	STRONGLY AGREE

Table 2.1-2.4 proposed that social media shaming is extensively viewed as a serious risk to teachers' emotional well-being and professional standing. The respondents consistently show a strong agreement that online shaming induce to mental health challenges, declined motivation, and Reputational harm. There is also a clear call for institutional protections to help educators recover and maintain their dignity in the face of public scrutiny.

TABLE 3.1. VIRAL POSTS AND HASHTAGS

Viral Posts and Hashtags	MEAN	Adjectival Description
1. How often do you see posts related to shaming going viral on your social media feed?	2.83	Often
2. How frequently do you come across trending hashtags that criticize or mock someone?	2.7	Rarely
3. How often do people in your online community share shaming content?	2.36	Often
4. How frequently do you engage with (like/share/comment) on shaming-related viral posts?	1.76	Rarely
5. How often do you notice that shaming posts receive more attention than positive ones?	2.8	Rarely

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Average 2.49 Rarely

TABLE 3.2. PUBLIC CALL-OUTS OR CANCEL CULTURE

Public Call-Outs or Cancel Culture	MEAN	Adjectival Description
1. How often do you witness individuals being publicly "called out" on social media?	2.83	Often
2. How frequently do you see someone being "canceled" online for their actions or opinions?	2.53	Often
3. How often do you encounter posts where someone's mistake is exaggerated for public criticism?	2.6	Rarely
4. How frequently do online users demand punishment or accountability from the person being shamed?	2.73	Often
5. How often do you see call-out posts becoming a source of entertainment or gossip?	2.83	Often
Average	2.7	Rarely

TABLE 3.3. EMOTIONAL AND REPUTATIONAL IMPACT ON VICTIMS

Emotional and Reputational Impact on Victims	MEAN	Adjectival Description
1. How often do you see victims of social media shaming expresses emotional distress publicly?	2.7	Rarely
2. How frequently do you encounter stories where a person's reputation was damaged due to online shaming?	2.8	Rarely
	2.36	Rarely

3. How often do you see individuals apologizing or deactivating accounts after being shamed?		
4. How frequently do people mention feeling anxious or fearful after being criticized online?	2.76	Often
5. How often do you see online shaming affecting a person's job, relationships, or public image?	2.93	Often
Average	2.71	Often

TABLE 3.4. INCREASE IN DIGITAL FOOTPRINT MONITORING

Increase in Digital Footprint Monitoring	MEAN	Adjectival Description
1. How often do you think twice before posting something due to fear of being shamed?	3.16	Often
2. How frequently do you see people deleting old posts to avoid online criticism?	2.63	Often
3. How often do users in your network edit or filter their content to avoid backlash?	2.66	Often
4. How frequently do you or others use private settings to avoid public scrutiny?	2.86	Often
5. How often do you observe people advising others to "be careful what you post"?	2.83	Often
Average	2.83	Often

Table 3.1 – 3.4 indicates active participation in shaming content was low but this does not eliminate its presence and consequences. The consequences, such as viral posts, public shaming, and emotional aftermath are enough to compel a change of behavior with many individuals moderating their online activities to escape being victims of shaming. All of this represents a digital

ecology that requires safeguarding and self-censorship to achieve some measure of safety socializing in the open and public ramifications.

Significant Difference Between Teacher's Perceptions of Social Media Shaming in terms of Profile of the Respondents

PROFILE	F VALUE	SIG	DECISION	Adjectival Description
Sex	5.292	.029	REJECT H ₀	Significant
Age	.644	.533	ACCEPT H ₀	Not significant
Academic department	1.251	.312	ACCEPT H ₀	Not significant
Educational Attainment	1.105	.376	ACCEPT H ₀	Not significant

Table 4 shows that only sex was significantly different between the perceptions of teachers about social media shaming ($p = .029$). This implies that male and female teachers respond and interpret online shaming differently. There were no significant differences between age, academic department, and educational attainment.

Significant Difference Between the Prevalence of Social Media Shaming on Teachers in terms of Profile of the Respondents

PROFILE	F VALUE	SIG	DECISION	INTERPRETATION
Sex	3.760	.063	ACCEPT H ₀	NOT SIGNIFICANT
Age	1.525	.236	ACCEPT H ₀	NOT SIGNIFICANT
Academic department	.140	.935	ACCEPT H ₀	NOT SIGNIFICANT
Educational attainment	1.929	.137	ACCEPT H ₀	NOT SIGNIFICANT

As shown in Table 5, there was no statistically significant effect of social media shaming on gender, age, department, or education. This supports the idea that all teachers are at risk of social media shaming, regardless of their age, sex, department, or educational attainment.

A correlation analysis was used. There is a weak positive correlation ($r = .274$) between

		Average of perceptions	Average of prevalence
Average of Perceptions	pearson correlation	1	.274
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.143
	N	30	30
Average of Prevalence	pearson correlation	.274	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.143	
	N	30	30

perceptions and prevalence of social media shaming; however, it was not statistically significant ($p = .143$). It indicates that there is no significant relationship between the teachers' perceptions about social media shaming and its prevalence.

CONCLUSION

The study's findings demonstrate the impact of social media shaming through consequences for faculty members' emotions and careers in Higher education. The respondents strongly agreed that these kinds of experiences were upsetting, damaging one's reputation and affecting how the public views educators.

Although the relationship between perceived incidence of shaming and actual experience of shaming did not demonstrate statistically significant, it is evident from the overall responses that there remains a culture of vulnerability and concern for faculty. Hence, these results indicate that there is a need for interventions that are proactive, both in policy and psychosocial, to protect the safety of educators and to safeguard the integrity of the profession in a digital terrain.

RECOMMENDATION

This paper urges the educational institution to enhance faculty well-being, accountability, reputation, and digital safety through establishing a faculty wellness program with counseling support to reduce burnout and promote mental health and implementing a formal Anti-Digital Harassment Policy with reporting mechanisms to protect faculty rights and ensure accountability. A public relations campaign should highlight teachers' achievements to improve the institution's reputation and counter negative perceptions. Regular training on digital literacy and online safety will empower faculty to manage their online presence and handle digital threats effectively. Additionally, a monitoring and evaluation committee should be created to track incidents, assess interventions, and guide data-driven decisions for adapting strategies. These measures collectively aim to foster a supportive, resilient academic community equipped to navigate the challenges posed by social media in education.

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